

REVIEW ARTICLE

Coexistence of public & private health systems in India: A review

Vibhav Garg^{1*}, Salma Ahmed²

¹ AIMA-AMU Ph.D. Program Candidate, Director-Govt Affairs Strategy, India, HUB & ASEAN, Boston Scientific, Bestech Business Tower, 3rd Floor, Sector 48, Gurugram, 122018, Haryana
² Professor, Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Studies & Research, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, 202001, UP

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 07.10.2020

Accepted: 16.11.2020

Published: 22.12.2020

Citation: Garg V, Ahmed S (2020) Coexistence of public & private health systems in India: A review. Indian Journal of Medicine and Healthcare 7(1): 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJMh/v7i1.1>

* **Corresponding author.**

vibhav99@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2020 Garg & Ahmed. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.iseeadyar.org/))

ISSN

Print: 2278-3334

Electronic: 2278-2966

Abstract

Objective: To provide a brief review of the coexistence of the public and private healthcare systems in India. **Method/Statistical Analysis:** The researcher reviewed various secondary sources including journals, research articles and reports from other sources like all five-year plans of Govt of India, National Health Policy 2002 & 2017. This enabled the researcher to provide a detailed outlook of the healthcare scenario in India, pre and post-independence conditions and public-private sector collaborations. In order to access the authentic data/information, the researcher has consulted various authentic databases, portals, books and documents like National Health Portal of India (www.nhp.gov.in), Open Government Data (OGD) Platform India (<https://data.gov.in/sector/health>), Health System Database at National Health Systems Resource Center (<http://nhsrcindia.org/health-systems-database>), The Imperial Gazetteer of India, Public Health in British India: Anglo-Indian Preventive Medicine, etc, which collectively span over a period of more than 16 decades from 1859 to 2020. The analysis method is descriptive, consisting of tables, graphs and textual representation. **Findings:** The public and the private healthcare sectors in India face certain challenges such as weak infrastructure including non-availability of drugs, lack of advanced laboratory facilities & equipment, a severely constrained health workforce, poorly financed public health system along with a poor delivery mechanism for health care for public health and high cost, significantly focused around bigger towns, mostly out-of-pocket for private health. Additionally, heightened demand for timely and affordable quality healthcare services and low penetration of health insurance in the country were also adding to the health burden. Thus, the country requires significant reforms to balance and address the quoted bottlenecks. The collaboration of the public and the private sector to provide better healthcare services has come up as an important alternative. Such collaboration would help in countering the challenges and make them more accountable. **Application:** This study finds applicability in academia and practice, as the findings of this study can be used to bridge the gap in existing knowledge regarding the assessment of the challenges facing public

and private healthcare institutions when operating as standalone systems. Moreover, the findings can be applied to other developing countries where similar problems in the healthcare space are encountered.

Keywords: Healthcare; India; public health; private health; health insurance; RSBY; Ayushman Bharat; PMJAY; CGHS

1 Introduction

The healthcare industry of an economy plays an important role in the quality of life and social welfare within the society and this has been well recognized⁽¹⁾. As stated by Harrison⁽²⁾, the relationship between health and economics is dynamic and complex and has generally gone unappreciated. Also being an important component of human capital, health is normally viewed as an integral input for the productivity of a nation, akin to other conventional inputs such as labor and physical capital. However, health is different from these other factors since it is multidimensional and is represented by a variety of indicators such as life expectancy and infant mortality rate⁽³⁾. Also, with the growing importance of the healthcare industry in public finance, it has become a dominant economic and political issue. The efficiency and the effectiveness of this sector in India have often been questioned, evoking the age-old controversial debate regarding the coexistence of public and private healthcare systems in recent years⁽⁴⁾. The present study in this context provides a brief review of the benefits of the coexistence of both these healthcare systems in India. In this regard, the present study will touch upon the areas such as the scenario of healthcare in India, healthcare industry pre- and post-independence, ongoing efforts for public and private collaboration, their efficiency, and finally, the public-private partnership.

2 Significance of the study

The Indian economy since independence has faced various issues with respect to affordability and accessibility when it comes to quality healthcare, with the majority of its people who are living below the poverty line and around 70 percent of its population dwelling in rural areas. In light of all these facts highlighted providing healthcare services to this part of the population should be the key concern of the policies being drafted by the government. Considering the present situation, the Indian healthcare system has been standing at crossroads. Even though the healthcare system has taken certain leaps by increasing accessibility and affordability through collaborating the public and private healthcare system, the delivery system comprising both public and private has continued to remain elusive to the various sections of society that have high healthcare needs. Evaluating the situation on statistical grounds it has been found that India on average registers the death of around 9.5 million people. Where 27 percent are due to cardiovascular diseases, infectious and parasitic disease-account for 20 percent, respiratory infections such as pneumonia are at 11%, respiratory diseases like Asthma, COPD with 9% and around 8% deaths are due to cancer. Considering this present situation and in order to encounter this voluminous disease burden, India requires a proper healthcare structure that comprises an appropriate combination of public and private healthcare. However, the economy has not been able to successfully raise healthcare spending (public + private) to more than 5 percent of GDP when compared with the global average of 10.1%. Also, the economy still has been grappling with the issue of the severe shortage of doctors and nurses which currently are half of the norm of 24.5 healthcare professionals per 10,000 population. Thus, until the government works in collaboration with other stakeholders like the private sector on priority. The Indian economy is likely to miss the targets that have been set in order to achieve the basic rights of citizens such as health. The following study will focus on reflecting on the gaps

in the healthcare system and how the possible collaboration of public and private healthcare systems at various places can solve that issue.

3 Research methodology

The present study is based on secondary data resources. Pre-existing data was collected and reviewed, which eventually helped the researcher in the formation of the framework for the study, determining the gaps that have been left in previous literature. The secondary resources through which the data have been majorly collected include business reports, books, publications, articles in magazines, newspapers and journal articles. With respect to the period considered for the present study the researcher included both pre and post-independence sources, i.e. before and after 1947, for assessing the condition of healthcare in India. The databases consulted in this regard were as follows: JSTOR, Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, Springer, Sage, ResearchGate, SSRN, Google Books and various other publications. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study are stated as follows.

Inclusion criteria

- Studies published in or after the year 2000.
- Studies that were related to the core themes of private and public healthcare in India and keywords targeted were used.
- Studies that were published in the English language.
- Studies for which full information and data was available.

Exclusion criteria

- Studies which were published before the year 2000.
- Studies that were published in vernacular or local languages.
- Studies for which full report or information was unavailable.
- Studies that did not make use of the keywords set beforehand for this study.

Furthermore, the analysis of this study makes use of graphs, tables and text. No software was used in this process.

4 Healthcare scenario in India

According to IBEF the Indian healthcare system has merged to become one of India's largest sectors both in terms of its revenue-generating capacity and employment creation. The Indian healthcare system has been divided into three major segments which include primary, secondary and tertiary care. The healthcare delivery system in India is an admixture of public and private sector providers which has resulted in the evolution of a competitive, performance-driven industry that demands the topmost management with respect to workforce, technology and finance⁽⁵⁾. In some years India has witnessed increasing demand for health care facilities mainly on the ground of factors such as aging population, rising income levels, growing health awareness, and change in people's attitude towards preventive healthcare. However, due to the presence of certain gaps in the public healthcare system with respect to human resources, access and quality have resulted in an unprecedented growth of the private sector in the country. Certain features of the private sector such as seamless delivery of services both in rural and urban areas along with timely approach and better information technology system adopted have strengthened the sector and have thus concentrated more patients towards itself⁽⁶⁾. Further, the scenario is changing rapidly as in a developing country like India, citizens' expectations regarding the quality of healthcare are undergoing a metamorphosis. Increased exposure to global healthcare systems through sources of information such as the internet and forms of mass media are making people more informed regarding their health and various treatment options available for leading as well as rare diseases. Thus the demand for timely affordable care and the latest treatments is on the rise⁽⁷⁾.

Considering the scenario at the time of independence, the public sector was the forefront provider of healthcare services and at that time the private sector accounted for only 8% of total patients care. However, presently, 93% of hospitals, 64% of beds, 80%-85% of doctors and 80% of outpatients and 57% of inpatients services are being catered by the private sector. Further, as per the NSS survey more than 70% spells of ailment have been treated by the private sector which included private doctors, nursing homes, private hospitals, charitable institutions etc.⁽⁸⁾. The people's inclination towards the private health sector can also be discovered from the NFHS-4 report. According to the report, 56.1% and 49% of people belonging to urban and rural areas respectively have sought to take private healthcare services in times of sickness. While considering the figure for public sector it was 42% and 46.4% respectively. However, in terms of health insurance, the public sector has wider coverage but when considering the overall situation with respect to infrastructure, like health enterprise, doctors, medical colleges, the contribution of the private sector is greater than the government sector⁽⁹⁾. However, it cannot also be denied that the Indian healthcare

industry is accredited as one of the fastest-growing industries and is expected to grow at an annual compound growth rate of 17% for the period counting from 2011 to 2022, touching US \$280 billion in size⁽⁹⁾. The industry has also been ranked among the top three healthcare markets in the world with respect to the incremental growth up to the period of 2022⁽¹⁰⁾.

However, a major problem that has been identified as a roadblock in this industry is the low penetration of medical and health insurance, particularly in rural areas. Only 27% of the Indian population is covered under government health financing schemes. Moreover, the selection criteria adopted by the suppliers also restrict the poor from taking advantage of affordable prepayment schemes. Lack of insurance coverage has forced many in India below the poverty line due to the healthcare expenditure. Further, it has been found that nearly 40% of the people who were admitted in various hospitals during 1995-1996 have fallen into debt on account of healthcare expenses, majorly hospitalization^{(11) (12)}.

5 Infectious diseases

The emergence of infectious diseases has always been a matter of serious concern for all economy. At present, the world has been impacted by Covid-19 infection on an unprecedented scale. The emergence of such types of infectious diseases has the potential to cause a public health emergence that can have a serious impact on the wellbeing of the community, health system, steadiness of national economies and eventually the progress towards sustainable development goals. Further one of the major challenges that the system might face combating such diseases is their unpredictable nature that has the capability to make it difficult to tackle the disease⁽¹³⁾. Considering the situation with respect to the Indian economy infectious diseases have been responsible for almost half of the total disease burden. Some of the major event of healthcare concern that occurred in India includes an outbreak of cholera, diphtheria, scrub typhus, Nipah virus encephalitis, chandipur virus, H5HI, H1NI, chikungunya and Japanese encephalitis are some of the major examples. The presence of such infectious diseases increases the need for effective collaboration on healthcare security and pandemic preparedness⁽¹⁴⁾. However, the grossly underfunded and patchy public healthcare system in India along with the huge variation in different states possess significant challenges for the country with respect to a disease containment strategy. Although, India has still made certain achievements with respect to controlling infectious diseases however it has still not proceeded to control many old, new and resurgent infectious diseases. The major cause of this is a deficiency in the public healthcare system of India which has although focused on technologically advancing medical care for the urban elite population but lacks an adversely functional public health infrastructure which is significantly essential for the prevention of diseases in all communities⁽¹⁵⁾.

6 Challenges in private healthcare sector and role of government in reducing cost

Although the private healthcare sector of India has an inherent trait of profit-making and also the private sector has the potential to provide preventive and curative healthcare services. However, the failure of the public sector while assigning the PMPs is one of the major bottlenecks that the Indian healthcare sector. Another major challenge that has been witnessed in the private sector is difficulty in enforcing regulations due to the presence of factors such as heterogeneity of institutions, lack of standardized cost, variability in terms of infrastructure, workforce, and majorly the gap in the legislative implementation of the existing regulations⁽¹⁶⁾. In order to solve this issue following steps can be taken like mandatory accreditation of private institutions such as national accreditation for testing and calibration laboratories (NABL) and national accreditation board for hospitals and healthcare providers (NABH) could be a welcoming move in order to comply with quality standards. Further another significant hurdle present in mobilizing private providers is a huge cost that patients need to incur while availing of these services. And hence it becomes essential to regulate the fees of this sector. At present there are three different payment methods are prevalent which include flexible fee schedule, fixed fee schedule and fee-sharing system⁽¹⁷⁾. Out of these flexible fees, schedules is most widely used where patients are required to pay fees directly to physicians and there is no control over physician charges. Hence this calls for an urgent need of introducing fee capping of services in different categories like diagnostic, inpatient, surgical, and outpatient services⁽¹⁸⁾ West Bengal clinical establishment bill and Karnataka private medical establishment in this respect has taken commendable steps like fixing rates of private healthcare services like laboratory investigation, intensive care and implants. Further another step specifies that in case there is a change in treatment with respect to the complication that arises hospitals are not allowed to charge anything extra. Also, regulations has also been specified like no demand for dues while handing over the dead body and hefty penalty have been set in case of non-compliance with regulations⁽¹⁹⁾.

7 Presence of private sector in India and how it has helped to overcome challenges faced by public healthcare sector of India

The presence of Indian healthcare sector can be traced back to the time of independence. Since the time of independence, the Indian policy framework has undergone various changes in terms of the macroeconomic front. Starting from the initial years, it has been found that the private healthcare sector growth picked up slightly in year 1980s and then rose sharply during 1990s. Post that growth has been recorded in 1990s-91 which is the liberalization phase for the economy. Further, the growth took a sharper turn in the year 2000 when a considerable amount of liberalization policies were introduced in the Indian healthcare sector. The state was then the facilitator of the public sector rather than the regulator. The private sector since then has been supporting the public healthcare sector by overcoming the challenges. The first issue which is faced by the Indian economy is low and inadequate spending with respect to the public healthcare sector. In fact, spending has been significantly low than the required minimum level of resources. Thus, not meeting the minimum level of basic healthcare facilities in the country. The current healthcare spending has been as low as 1.2 percent of GDP which is not significantly lower than the global average but it is even recorded to be low than some middle-income countries even those who have GDP lower than that of India. This little public spending on healthcare confirms the little intervention from the side of the state and central government. Which has increased the inadequacy of services and has provided the private sector with leverage to exploit the healthcare market in India. Further confronting the major challenges which are faced by public sector hospitals thus includes deficient infrastructure, deficient manpower, unmanageable patient loads, equivocal quality of service and high pocket expenditure. The present-day private sector has considerably been successfully overcoming some of the major challenges of the public sector like providing with best infrastructural facilities, better technological equipment, and better-qualified doctors. Considering the patient loads, the private sector hospitals have a better management system than the public sector. The following section thus highlighted how the private sector can help and overcome the challenges face by the public sector thus contributing towards the overall improvement of the system.

8 Role of education in increasing and enhancing healthcare in rural areas

Even with the significant contributions towards the improvement of health, the health outcomes have still remain inadequate. The vast gap that still exists between the capabilities and actual reality of the health situation in India has focused the attention of governmental and non-governmental agencies towards rebuilding the public health system. Several other social determinates that are associated with behavioral risks like smoking, oral tobacco consumption, and alcohol abuse have aggravated the situation. Thus in this scenario, health education has emerged as the most viable approach and specifically in rural areas of India in order to strengthen public health⁽²⁰⁾. This health education among people can significantly offer a healthcare system a means through which people's health can be improved by enabling the behavioral change which basically requires the effort from the individual and engages them in a community-based intervention that can eventually enable healthy choices among people. Health education among people motivates people where they can easily accept the process of behavioral change by directly impacting their values, beliefs and attitude when it is deemed that an individual is at particular risk or has been affected by a certain disease or illness⁽²¹⁾. Further considering the scenario of India where the country is facing triple burden like existing communicable diseases, emerging and re-emerging communicable diseases and ever-increasing non-communicable diseases and lifestyle-related diseases⁽²²⁾. Since all these diseases are somewhere linked with behaviors and lifestyle at an individual or either at a community level. Thus bringing in behavioral changes through effective communication can be perceived as the most useful and effective tool in addressing public health problems. Further another major fact is personal cleanliness is very poor in rural India which is the root cause for ill health there. There are issues like lack of bathing, use of clean clothes, washing hands, cleaning nails, spitting everywhere, coughing and sneezing without using any cloth over nose and face. All such habits predispose people to various health hazards. Moreover, consumption of unsafe drinking water, improper disposal of human excreta and improper sanitation facilities have been a major reason of various diseases like diarrhea and dysentery in rural areas. Thus educating people through communication, street play, rally, public lectures or Pham plates can be useful solutions⁽²³⁾.

9 Healthcare industry in India: Post-Independence period

The structured health policy making and health planning in India is not a post-independence concept. Rather one of the most comprehensive health policies and the plan was documented on the eve of independence in the year 1946. The plan was a health survey and development committee report which is popularly referred as Bhore committee. The report was dedicated to preparing a plan for the National Health Service that can provide universal coverage to the entire population. The proposal of

Bhore committee required certain structural changes, which it would have been implemented properly could have brought radical transformations in the Indian healthcare structure. However, till date there is no evidence of the development of healthcare services to the level that Bhore committee had regarded as minimum standards⁽²⁴⁾.

In the post-colonial period, the Indian healthcare sector has witnessed the development of private medical practices as the core of the health sector. With the private sector initially strengthening the enclave sector and then an exploration of opportunities that increased with the expansion of socio-economic infrastructure. Up until 1982-83 India did not have any formal health policy statement. It was in 1983 that India adopted a formal or official national health policy. Prior to which all the health sector-related activities were part of five-year plans and the recommendations of various committees set up. In the year 1950s and 1960s the entire focus of the health sector was on managing the epidemics. This was followed by mass campaigns that were launched against diseases such as malaria, smallpox, tuberculosis, leprosy, trachoma and cholera⁽²⁵⁾. With the launch of the first two five-year plans the basic structure of the healthcare sector did not witness many changes. The urban areas were still getting the three-fourth of medical care resources whereas for the rural areas community development program was undertaken. However, the CDP failed even before the beginning of the second five-year plan. In order to evaluate the progress made by first two plans, Mudaliar committee was set up in 1959. The committee recorded certain achievements in terms of certain virulent diseases like malaria, cholera and smallpox and noticed an overall reduction in morbidity and mortality rate. The death rate for the period 1956-61 declined to 21.6 percent and life expectancy at the time of birth increased to 42 years. Further, the report also admitted that the primary healthcare programs are not given the importance they should have been given from the very start⁽²⁶⁾.

Further the third five-year plan which was launched in 1961 directed its attention towards the problems that have been affecting the PHCs, delay in construction of PHCs and inadequate training facilities of staff in the rural areas. Also, the plan mentioned the inadequacy of institutions, doctors in rural areas at the end of the second five-year plan. The fourth plan that began in the year 1969 was much more in the same lines as the third five-year plan. It was finally the fifth five-year plan that acknowledged the fact that even with the infant mortality rate going down and life expectancy increasing. The actual number of medical institutions, functionaries, beds and health facilities are still inadequate in rural areas. It was in this plan that the government acknowledged the fact that urban health has expanded at the cost of the rural sector. Whereas the sixth plan was highly influenced by Alma Ata declaration that was based on health for all. The seventh plan on another hand stated that the success of any plan clearly depends on efficiency, quality and texture of implementation⁽²⁷⁾. Since independence in 1947, various committees have been formed that worked towards improving the healthcare industry of India. This includes Bhore Committee, Mudaliar Committee, Chadha Committee, Mukherjee Committee, Jain Committee, Kartar Singh Committee, and the Srivastava Committee. The basic analysis of the major Committees' recommendations reflects the major changes and developments in the Indian healthcare industry. Thus, since independence, a considerable amount of progress has been achieved in the promotion of the healthcare industry. Some communicable diseases like smallpox have been completely eliminated, while mortality due to cholera and other related diseases have decreased significantly⁽²⁸⁾. Today, a few episodes of cholera continue to occur. Also, the situation related to public sanitation, preventive healthcare, systems for the control of communicable diseases, and education related to healthcare needs to be improved. In addition to diseases which are related to urbanization like diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, cancer have come up as the major cause of concern⁽²⁹⁾. Although there are many hospitals, dispensaries, and public health centers present, they are not enough to cater to the needs of the substantially growing population of India. Access to quality healthcare facilities in rural areas needs to improve. Along with this, another major cause for concern among healthcare authorities is inadequate manpower, i.e. doctors and nurses in public sector hospitals. Further, infrastructure requirements in hospitals like medicines, machinery and equipment and furniture are not enough to serve India's huge population. With the public healthcare sector facing all these issues, the private sector has been trying hard to overcome them. A large number of private hospitals are set up in order to meet the healthcare needs of the vast population of India. Along with this government has from time to time appointed various committees and initiated various programs with the aim of addressing the pervasive problems of the healthcare sector⁽³⁰⁾. A few of these programs are Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY), National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), Pradhan Mantri Swasthya Suraksha Yojana (PMSSY), National Programme for Prevention & Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases & Stroke (NPCDCS).

Also, in terms of expenditure on the health sector in India since independence, a certain amount of budget has been always allocated to the private sector. The health expenditure in India is presented in [Table 1](#) below which represents the expenditure on health as part of the various Five-year plans of India.

10 Healthcare developments in India: National health policy (NHP)

Health and health-related issues of citizens are important and are of grave concern for the government of a country. The government is responsible to provide quality healthcare services to its citizens. In order to enable this, the Indian government

Table 1. Health expenditure of India (Rupees in Million)⁽³¹⁾

Five-year plans	Period	Total plan investment	Health expenditure (percent of total plan)
First	1951-1956	1,960	3.33
Second	1956-1961	4,672	3.01
Third	1961-1966	8,576.5	2.63
Annual	1966-1969	6,625.4	2.12
Fourth	1969-1974	15,778.8	2.13
Fifth	1974-1979	39,426.2	1.93
	1979-1980	12,176.5	1.83
Sixth	1980-1985	97,500	1.87
Sixth	1980-1985	1,09,291.7	1.85
Seventh	1985-1990	1,80,000	1.88
Seventh	1985-1990	2,18,729	1.69
	1990-1991	61,518	1.56
	1991-1992	65,855	1.58
Eighth	1992-1997	4,34,100	1.75
Ninth	1997-2002	8,59,200	0.6
Tenth	2002-2007	15,92,300	-

shifted from a committee-based to a policy-based approach in the year 1983 with the formulation of the first National Health Policy⁽¹⁷⁾.

National health policy, 1983

The main objective of the first-ever health policy was to devise the mechanism to be able to provide quality and comprehensive healthcare services to all Indians by 2000. The major aspects of the policy included a preventive, promote and rehabilitative primary health care approach, expansion of private curative sector which would help in reducing the burden of the government sector, identification of health issues that require urgent attention, stabilization of the population, provision of health education and the establishment of the medical industry, health insurance and medical research⁽¹⁸⁾. Considering the policy achievements the rural health care received special attention and expansion of primary healthcare facilities was undertaken. However, there were shortcomings as well as the policy was not able to reflect the ground realities. And the task that was undertaken in policy was not sufficient in order to meet the demand of the masses and especially of those who were living in rural areas.

National health policy, 2002

Since NHP 1983, there had been significant changes in the determinants of health necessitating the revision of NHP and a new NHP has evolved. The second National Health Policy was formulated in the year 2002 which was nearly 20 years after the formulation of the first one. At the time, India needed financial investments and organizational structure so that the Indian healthcare sector can well respond to diversities in the market. There was number of objectives that were attempted to address through NHP 2002, mainly focused on achieving an acceptable standard of good health of Indian Population through decentralization of the public health system by upgrading infrastructure in existing institutions.

Along with these objectives, few timebound goals were also determined in NHP 2002 such as eradication of Polio & Leprosy by 2005, achieve Zero level growth of HIV/AIDS by 2007, an increase of 2010 State sector Health spending from 7% to 8%

The strategies formulated tried to work on three pillar model that not only helped achieve the above-mentioned objectives and goals but also redefined the sector i.e. financing, organization, and regulation⁽¹⁹⁾.

National rural health mission (NRHM) (2005)

After few years of releasing National Health Policy 2002 and during Tenth Five Year Plan, the then Prime Minister of India launched **National Rural Health Mission (NRHM)** in 2005, to provide accessible, affordable and quality health care to the rural population, especially the vulnerable groups.

NRHM was created to provide equitable, affordable and quality health care to the rural population, especially the vulnerable groups, which continues. The thrust of the mission is on establishing a fully functional, community-owned, decentralized health delivery system with inter-sectoral convergence at all levels, to ensure simultaneous action on a wide range of determinants of health such as water, sanitation, education, nutrition, social and gender equality. Institutional integration within the fragmented health sector was expected to provide a focus on outcomes, measured against Indian Public Health Standards for all health

Area	Initiative taken
Financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation of 55%, 35% and 10% of the budget to the primary, secondary and tertiary healthcare sectors. • Extending 2% of the health budget for the purpose of medical research by 2010. • Providing healthcare services to the poor under the scheme known as social health insurance.
Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving local governments in public health implementation programs. • Setting up of well-organized primary health centers in urban areas. • Co-operation from the side of private health practitioners. • Creating an integrated disease control network. • Creating women-targeted healthcare programs.
Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formation of a Medical Grant Commission. • Increase in the seats of public health and family medicine. • Setting up of a legislation for the minimum standards of healthcare infrastructure by 2003. • Setting up of minimum quality standards by the year 2003.

facilities.

While NRHM was successfully resolving the health issues in rural India, it was equally challenging and important to address issues with urban health, which is extremely complex with a myriad of challenges. For urban health to expand comprehensively to address issues and effectively fulfill the demand of an ever-increasing vulnerable population, the **National Urban Health Mission (NUHM)** was launched in 2013. NUHM was aimed to address the health concerns of the urban population especially the poor and disadvantaged by facilitating equitable access to health services that are rationalized, revamped and strengthened.

The above two Sub-Missions, the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) and the National Urban Health Mission (NUHM) converge into the larger strategic platform named **National Health Mission (NHM)**. The main programmatic components of NHM include Health System Strengthening, Reproductive-Maternal- Neonatal-Child and Adolescent Health (RMNCH+A), and Communicable and Non-Communicable Diseases. The NHM envisages the achievement of universal access to equitable, affordable & quality health care services that are accountable and responsive to people's needs⁽²⁰⁾. (<https://nhm.gov.in/>)

National health policy, 2017

In 34 years since the first National Health Policy came into being in 1983, there have been major developments in the ways the health sector is been progressing in the country as well as the way healthcare services are delivered. These developments have also changed the priorities for the country that can be summarized as follows:

1. While IMR (infant mortality rate) and MMR (maternal mortality rate) have declined rapidly, we are witnessing a dual burden due to growing non-communicable diseases and some infectious diseases.
2. The emergence of a robust health care industry is estimated to be growing at double digit.
3. The growing incidences of catastrophic expenditure, owing to the majority of healthcare delivery in the private sector at a higher cost, are presently estimated to be one of the major contributors to poverty.
4. A rising economic growth enabling enhanced fiscal capacity.

Therefore, a new health policy responsive to these contextual changes as needed and the union government launched the recent National Health Policy in the year 2017. The main aim of the policy was to adopt the incremental assurance approach that can account for the changing priorities in India's healthcare delivery system. NHP 2017 specifically focused on preventive, promotive, curative, palliative and rehabilitative services with quality as well as various measures to achieve Universal Health Coverage by building more healthcare centers and reduction of spiraling expenditures in order to meet the widening healthcare financing deficits.

The government through these policies has played an important role in improving the status of healthcare infrastructure and delivery in the country. These policies help strengthen the system and support the generation of human, financial and other resources, thus enabling the achievement of their goals of improving the health of the general population and reducing inequalities therein⁽²¹⁾.

Govt health insurance/Health scheme(s)

With drastic measures taken in the form of National Health Policies, India has achieved major changes in terms of health improvements. Government-funded healthcare services have always been criticized for quality and access. In such a scenario the private sector is known to bridge the gap between government offerings and people's needs⁽²²⁾. However, a major concern remains that with the proliferation of private healthcare services, there is an equal rise in the cost of care, which eventually becomes unaffordable for a large section of the population. In such cases, there is an urgent need to explore various health financing ways in order to address the complexities that have been arising with the growth of the private health sector⁽²³⁾.

Govt Health Insurance Schemes and Govt Health Schemes play an important role in these circumstances. While govt health insurance scheme, in general, can be defined as the project where individuals or groups are provided health coverages by virtue of govt paying a fee which is known as a 'premium' to a predesignated insurance organization, govt health scheme is a more reimbursement scheme wherein the beneficiaries are reimbursed the total episodic cost by the respective govt organization.

Govt health insurance, although being a well-established concept in developed countries, is relatively new in India. Other than employees of the organized sector, only 2 percent of India's health expenditure is funded by the public sector or by social health insurance. Only 18% is funded by the government's healthcare budget⁽²⁴⁾. However, with liberalization and the new economic policies that have been adopted in India, privatization of the health insurance sector has taken place. The health insurance sector which earlier remained highly underdeveloped is now being poised to bring about fundamental changes in the Indian healthcare sector⁽²⁵⁾.

Central Government Health Scheme (CGHS) is one such and the pioneer scheme, which was started in 1954 and provides comprehensive health care facilities for 3.5 million Central Govt. employees and pensioners and their dependents residing in CGHS covered 71 cities in India (<https://cghs.gov.in/>)⁽²⁶⁾.

As CGHS was only covering a designated lot of people and a high budget scheme, Govt of India came out with an insurance-based scheme for below poverty line population in the country naming **Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY)**. RSBY was launched in early 2008 and was initially designed to target only the Below Poverty Line (BPL) households but was later expanded to cover other defined categories of unorganized workers as well. RSBY was also the first experiment of Govt of India for demand-side financing of healthcare. The premium cost for enrolled beneficiaries under the scheme was shared by Government of India and the State Governments. The program had the target to cover 70 million households by the end of the Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-17) and was adopted by 29 states in 2014. Its main service delivery model remained as demand financing, freedom of choice among accredited government and private hospitals, and cashless service reimbursable to the provider on pre-determined package rates on family floater basis, became a strong pillar for the universal health care system envisioned by Government of India (<http://www.rsby.gov.in/>)⁽²⁷⁾⁽²⁸⁾.

While central government has been working on various models mentioned above, state governments have been highly forthcoming as well by launching various health insurance schemes for their respective states. Primarily these schemes covered the most vulnerable sections of the society i.e. below the poverty line population of these states⁽²⁹⁾. A few of these schemes are Rajiv Aarogyasri (Combined Andhra Pradesh, 2007), Vajpayee Arogyashree (Karnataka, 2010; Now known as Arogya Karnataka), Chief Minister's Comprehensive Health Insurance Scheme (Tamil Nadu, 2009), etc.

The latest addition to the list of health schemes in India is the largest health schemes ever announced anywhere in the world in terms of coverage i.e. **Ayushman Bharat-Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (AB-PMJAY)**. PMJAY proposes to cover more than 10 crores of poor and vulnerable families (about 50 crore beneficiaries) to provide health services worth Rs. 5 lakhs per family per year for secondary and tertiary care hospitalization. When conceptualized, the scheme was coined as National Health Protection Scheme (NHPS) but later it was renamed as PMJAY. As PMJAY was expected to provide health coverage to almost bottom 40% of the Indian population, it subsumed the then-existing Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) which had been launched in 2008. PMJAY is primarily a Government-funded scheme, while implementation cost is shared between the Central and State Governments⁽³⁰⁾.

11 Ongoing effort in Public-Private collaboration in healthcare

In India, the private health sector is growing markedly. However, it has been found that millions of people are impoverished and thus run into massive debts to access healthcare. Thus, healthcare and its delivery still stand as a big challenge in India. Further, it has been suggested that awareness about health issues, accessibility of health services, availability of human resources in health facilities affordability of healthcare services and accountability for chosen procedures and processes are the five main things that the Indian healthcare system needs to achieve sooner than later⁽³¹⁾. In India, public spending on health is around 1.2 percent of its GDP which is said to be the lowest in the world. Hence, there is an urgent need to increase its public spending to at least 3 percent of its GDP by the year 2020 and 4 percent by the year 2025⁽³²⁾.

Since each sector whether public or private has certain deficiencies in the health system, the country requires significant reforms. The collaboration of the public and private sector and hence fostering a partnership in order to provide better healthcare services has come up as an important alternative. Harnessing the private sector energy and findings from the public sector can be helpful in countering the failures of both the public and private sector, thus making them more accountable⁽³³⁾. The government of India over the last few decades has focused on various public-private collaborations in the healthcare industry in order to address public needs. Some of the ongoing collaborations include the contractual appointment of private practitioners for providing services in PHCs, allowing state government doctors to carry private practices as well, including NGOs in the national healthcare programs, giving permission for the duty-free imports of the medical equipment at concessional rates,

private practitioners providing information and creating awareness regarding certain diseases in the districts and the latest in the series is empanelment of private hospitals in PMJAY⁽³⁴⁾ ⁽³⁵⁾. Further, owing to the scarcity which is present public healthcare sector of India two distinctive approaches can be adopted that can increase public-private partnership and through which the private sector can overcome the challenges of the public sector. The first strategy could be to attract private investment which is based on a philanthropic basis along with maintaining the bureaucratic management of the existing healthcare facilities. Further, another strategy could be increasing private sector participation by handling the management of public sector healthcare⁽³⁶⁾.

12 Efficiency in public and private healthcare system

The public health sector of India has made great strides in providing appropriate healthcare services to the vast population of the country. During the period 1990 to 2007, the public sector's healthcare infrastructure has gone up from 725 facilities to around 163,000 which includes 4000 rural sub-district hospitals, 24000 primary healthcare centers and 135,000 sub-health centers. Yet it falls short in covering the large population of India. The major drawbacks faced by the public sector not only includes infrastructure shortage but also in terms of highly qualified practitioners who can provide quality services⁽³⁷⁾.

While the private healthcare industry has been responding aggressively in order to meet the healthcare demands, the major reason that private sector services outperform those of the public sector is that private sector hospitals are generally characterized by the specialty doctors, staff, nurses and world-class infrastructure with all cutting-edge technologies. Moreover, in terms of supporting infrastructures such as cleanliness and sanitation, services are better than the public sector⁽³⁸⁾.

13 Conclusion

The Indian healthcare industry has come a long way, from the ancient times when the ayurvedic medicines prevailed then moving on to the Unani approach under the Mughal regime and then finally making a transition into modern medicine, witnessing many changes along the way. However, even after the years of establishment, the Indian industry sector has certain loopholes. For example, the private healthcare sector is not affordable for the majority of the population. Public sector, on the other hand, has its own shortcomings in terms of infrastructure, equipment, staff and doctors. Thus, the right balance between public and private healthcare services in need is what the country needs right now in order to completely satisfy the healthcare needs of the population.

References

- 1) Theodoropoulos S. On the effectiveness of Publicly or Privately produced Health care services. 2011.
- 2) Weil DN. Accounting for the effect of health on economic growth. *Q J Econ.* 2007;122(3):1265–1306.
- 3) Menon N. Synthesis paper Health policy and economic growth in India. *Lessons from International Growth Center Projects.* 2017.
- 4) Nath A. Health economics: Importance for public health in India. *JK Sci.* 2008;10(4):206–207.
- 5) Yoong J, Burger N, Spreng C, Sood N. Private Sector Participation and Health System Performance in Sub-Saharan Africa. *PLoS ONE.* 2010;5(10). Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0013243>.
- 6) Brugha R, Zwi A. Improving the Quality of Private Sector Delivery of Public Health Services: Challenges and Strategies. *Health Policy and Planning.* 1998;13(2):107–120. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/heapol/13.2.107>.
- 7) J Y, S T, Y T. Using Economic evaluation in policy decision-making in Asian countries: Mission impossible or mission probable? *Value Heal.* 2009;12(3):26–30.
- 8) Kumar G, et al. Utilisation, equity and determinants of full antenatal care in India: analysis from the National Family Health Survey 4. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2019;19(1):327.
- 9) Arulmohi M, Vinayagamoorthy V, R DA. Physical Violence Against Doctors: A Content Analysis from Online Indian Newspapers. *Indian J Community Med.* 2017;42(1):147–150.
- 10) Dang A, Likhari N, Alok U. Importance of Economic Evaluation in Health Care: An Indian Perspective. *Value in Health Regional Issues.* 2016;9(6):78–83. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.vhri.2015.11.005>.
- 11) Niëns LM, Cameron A, de Poel EV, Ewen M, Brouwer WBF, Laing R. Quantifying the Impoverishing Effects of Purchasing Medicines: A Cross-Country Comparison of the Affordability of Medicines in the Developing World. *PLoS Medicine.* 2010;7(8). Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000333>.
- 12) Chokshi M, et al. Health systems in India. *J Perinatol.* 2016;36(s3):9–12.
- 13) Ambat AS, Vyas N. Assessment of preparedness against emerging infectious disease among private hospitals in a district of South India. *Medical Journal Armed Forces India.* 2020. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mjafi.2020.02.007>.
- 14) Chetterje P. Gaps in India's preparedness for COVID-19 control. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases.* 2020;20(5). Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099\(20\)30300-5](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099(20)30300-5).
- 15) John TJ, Dandona L, Sharma VP, Kakkar M. Continuing challenge of infectious diseases in India. *The Lancet.* 2011;377(9761):252–269. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(10\)61265-2](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(10)61265-2).
- 16) Kumar A. Disease surveillance: engaging the private sector, Niti Ayog. 2015.
- 17) Garg S. Healthcare Policy in India- Challenges and Remedies. 2018.

- 18) Bahuguna P, Guinness L, Sharma S, Chauhan AS, Downey L, Prinja S. Estimating the Unit Costs of Healthcare Service Delivery in India: Addressing Information Gaps for Price Setting and Health Technology Assessment. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*. 2020;18(5):699-711. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40258-020-00566-9>.
- 19) Wani NUHWNH. Health System in India: Opportunities and Challenges for Enhancements. *J Bus Manag*. 2013;9(2):74-82.
- 20) Pati S, Sharma K, Zodpey S, Chauhan K, Dobe M. Health Promotion Education in India: Present Landscape and Future Vistas. *Global Journal of Health Science*. 2012;4(4):159-167. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v4n4p159>.
- 21) Jilani A, et al. Private providers of Healthcare in India: A policy analysis. *Internet J Third World Med*. 2012;8(1):1-5.
- 22) Amin W. Effective awareness generation methods for rural sanitation campaign: A study from a village in Haryana. *Int J Sociol Anthropol*. 2013;5(3):78-83.
- 23) Selvam V, Ashok D, Pratheepkanth P. Awareness and perception of health issues among rural women. *Int J Recent Technol Eng*. 2019;7(5):12-17.
- 24) Amrith SS. 2009.
- 25) Williams R. Health policy. *Nurs Manage*. 2016;23(1).
- 26) Tabish S. Historical Development of Health Care in India. *Hosp Heal Serv Adm Princ Pract*. 2000;p. 23-28.
- 27) Abhiyan JS. Health System in India: Crisis and Alternatives;vol. 2. and others, editor. 2006.
- 28) Gupta M. Public health in India. *Hosp Prog*. 2006;28(4):119-122.
- 29) Powell M. Health policy. In: and others, editor. Soc. policy. 2014;p. 349-370.
- 30) Dagar SDM. Healthcare in India : Current state and key imperatives. and others, editor. 2015.
- 31) Mcneill D, . Human Development: The Power of the Idea1. *J Hum Dev*. 2007;8(1):5-22.
- 32) Bhat R, Mavalankar D. Health Insurance in India: Opportunities, Challenges and Concerns. 2000.
- 33) Ahuja R. Health Insurance for the Poor in India. 2004.
- 34) Ranganadhan S. Public-Private Partnership in Health Sector - Opportunities for better Health Care delivery. *IOSR J Nurs Heal Sci*. 2018;7(4):25-33.
- 35) Dahiya H. National health policy of india. *Int J Recent Sci Res*. 2018;10(5).
- 36) Purohit BC. Private initiatives and policy options: recent health system experience in India. *Health Policy and Planning*. 2001;16(1):87-97. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/heapol/16.1.87>.
- 37) Mavalankar D. Health system in india. 2013.
- 38) Rao P. The private health sector in India: a framework for improving the quality of care. *ASCI J Manag*. 2012;41(2):14-39.